

Learning new digital/computational skills to enhance my research

Template 2: A learning path template to support my growth in digital/computational research.

This template was designed for participants of the [ESCALATOR EMPOWER](#) track to encourage intentional learning within a supportive online learning community.

Find this template online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6563415>

How to use this template:

1. Make a copy of the [Google Doc](#), download it as Word or PDF document, or print it out - whichever you prefer.
2. For optimal results, complete Template 1 (Reflection template) before attempting to complete Template 2 (Learning path template).
3. Read through the questions in this document before moving on to the next steps.
4. Use your responses in Template 1 to prioritise the tools, platforms, and methodologies that would be most beneficial for you to learn in the next few weeks/months (short term).
5. Identify one tool, platform, or methodology that you would like to learn or learn to use better.
6. Complete the questions below to help you design your learning path and create a schedule for learning the new skill.
7. These are live documents. Keep them handy. Update them. Refer back to them to see where you were a few months ago.
8. Celebrate and share your progress and wins! It's important to pause regularly and look back to see how far you've come.
9. Don't do this alone. Join a learning community, form your own small group of co-learning peers, or reach out for support. Alternatively, you can go on this journey and share your progress via short blog posts, Tweets, or reporting back to your research group.
10. Let us know if you found this template useful? How can we improve it? You can email us at escalator@talarify.co.za.

This work was inspired by:

- <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/people-and-organizational-performance/our-insights/intentional-learning-in-practice-a-3x3x3-approach>
- <https://101innovations.wordpress.com/>

My SMART plan

What skill or technology do I want to learn?

Why do I want to learn this skill?

Where will I apply this skill?

When will I apply this skill?

Who can I learn with?

What resources do I need to learn this skill? E.g. course material, software licensing, computing infrastructure?

What prior knowledge do I need to learn this skill?

Where can I find training or learning resources?

When will I work on learning this skill? E.g. How many hours per week/month am I able to commit to learning and practicing this skill?

My SMART schedule

Month	Activities	Dates/Times
May	Complete this template Planning Finding resources Finding learning buddies	
June		
July		
August		
September		
October		
November		
December	Presentations showing what I learned, how I learned, and with whom I learned	

Notes

-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-

Other templates in this series

1. Template 1: A reflection template to support my growth in digital/computational research.
EMPOWER: Templates to support learning path development for growing digital/computational research skills (v1.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6563416>